

EXPANDING THE IMPORTANCE OF PATRIOTISM AND LOYALTY TO THE HOMELAND IN BERDAKH'S WORKS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes Berdakh's works written in the spirit of patriotism, its interpretation in our country, the originality of his works, the image of the Motherland.

Berdakh is a great poet of the Karakalpak people. The themes of his works are very rich. His poetry embodies a clear picture of the social and political life of the Karakalpak people for a century. The main theme of Berdakh's works is the social life of the Karakalpak people, the sad life of the Karakalpak people. He was a "nightingale of the desert" who shared the joys and sorrows of the people and sang it. Berdakh lived in a time of political inequality, darkness, oppression and injustice, and called on the people to fight for a free life, honor the good sons of the people, call the youth to be polite, educated, humble, to serve the people. He called on the people to be loyal, patient, courageous, brave and love honest work. He advocated for the freedom of women, wanting respected mothers, dear brides and young girls to be free. Berdakh's language was rich and understandable to the people. From Berdakh's beautiful small lyrical spoons, the content of his great works is a struggle for a free and happy life. That is why the people of Karakalpakstan love him so much.

Morality, manners, elegance and beauty play an important role in Berdakh's creative heritage. His poems contain valuable ideas about national and universal values, patriotism, friendship of peoples, and simple morals. According to the poet, some mullahs and eshons present themselves to the people as honest and pure. In practice, we see the opposite. The poet exposes their hypocrisy. In his moral views, Berdakh continued the best traditions of the East. In his poems "I sought", "For the people", "Better", "I need", he praised the honest work of people. According to him, the main duty of every person is to serve the people and their well-being. Another important aspect of Berdakh's moral views is to respect the people, especially the elderly, the weak and the disabled, the poor and the destitute, and to help them as much as possible. Like Navoi, Berdakh divides people into two groups: good and bad. When we say good man, we mean people who are wise, intelligent, knowledgeable, helpful, and good-natured, with all human qualities. The bad man, in Berdakh's view, is a national catastrophe, he does not value the people and his brother. In general, humanity is at the center of the poet's moral views. In many of his poems, Berdakh sought to inculcate the ideas of raising children, respecting adults, patriotism for the younger generation, love for his people, and friendship and brotherhood between peoples.

Berdakh's lyrical poems and epics reflect the social life of the Karakalpak people in the 18th and 19th centuries. He evaluates the events of his time and social relations as an intelligent poet. His works promote equality, humanity, justice and patriotism. Berdakh's work focuses on

the plight of the working people ("Not", "Tax", "This Year", "My Life", etc.). For the truth, the poet dreams of selfless fighters for the happiness and future of the working masses ("For the people", "I need", etc.). In the works "History", "Generations", "Omongeldi", "Azadosbiy", "Ernazarbiy" the poet proudly sings about national heroes. Berdakh's "Generations" is a chronicle of historical events, which deals with the life of the Karakalpak people and other Turkic peoples, and the origins of tribes and peoples. Berdakh exposes some greedy clerics ("Better", "Shekilli", etc.), defends women's rights, urges young people to love the country, to reach the heights of enlightenment ("To my son", "Do not be stupid", etc.).

In his poetic observations and outlook on life, Berdakh wishes the workers a happy life. As Berdakh thought about making the people happy, he asked Allah for help ("Help"), thought about happiness ("I sought"), dreamed of a just king ("Need"), and hoped to build a happy society. Berdakh's work is close to the traditions of folklore. Due to the diversity of his work, the ideological and artistic height of his works, he occupies a prominent place in the history of Karakalpak literature. Many of his works have been translated into Uzbek and other languages. The 170th anniversary of Berdakh's birth was widely celebrated in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan (1998). One of the alleys in Tashkent was named after Berdakh and a bust was erected. The poet's birthplace, Bozatov, also has a bust (1998). In Nukus, a statue of Berdakh was erected, a musical drama theater, a street and a school were named after Berdakh. Berdakh is a famous poet of the Karakalpak people, a real child. Many schools, streets, cinemas and libraries in Karakalpakstan are named after the poet. The Karakalpak State Prize named after Berdakh was also established. The award is given to the best work in the field of fiction, art and architecture. Irkutsk's literary, socio-political and philosophical ideas, imbued with a high humanitarian spirit, still retain their educational significance in the conditions of independence. The study of Berdakh's works and the search for his manuscripts began in the 1930s. After that, his poems and epics were published first in his native language and then in a number of other languages. An in-depth study of his life and work began. The attitude of our country to independence, to the life and work of Berdakh has changed radically. In 1998, by the decree of the President, the 180th anniversary of the birth of Berdimurat Kargabay oğlu Berdakh was widely celebrated. The Berdakh National Museum was established at the Berdakh Karakalpak State University. Every nation will have great children who will introduce their identity, national status and dignity to the world.

Every year on November 27 in our country the birthday of the great poet of Karakalpakstan Berdimurat Kargabay oğlu Berdakh is widely celebrated. In particular, in the cities and districts of Karakalpakstan, in places of spirituality and enlightenment, Berdakh events are held. Samples of his poems and epics are read. The image of Berdakh has become a symbol not only of Karakalpakstan, but also of the pride and pride of all Turkic peoples.

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